

Excess Enthalpies of Binary Mixtures of some Hydrocarbons

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In order to understand the intermolecular interaction of aromatic hydrocarbons with other non-electrolyte solvents having molecules of different shapes and sizes, excess molar enthalpies (H^E) of binary systems, namely, *o*-xylene+cyclohexane, *p*-xylene+cyclohexane and benzene+n-octane, have been determined at 300.05 K using an isothermal phase change calorimeter. The observed excess enthalpies have been interpreted in terms of the intermolecular interactions within the mixture. The experimental H^E data has been compared with the corresponding values obtained from Flory's theory for binary mixtures. For the studied systems, the contact interactions contribution to H^E is found to predominate the equation of state contribution.

STUDY of excess thermodynamic properties of liquid mixtures is important both for understanding the nature of interaction among the component molecules as well as to test the theories earlier proposed for liquid mixtures¹⁻³. In continuation of our earlier studies⁴⁻⁷ on the thermodynamic properties of binary non-electrolyte solutions consisting one of the components as hydrocarbon, the excess enthalpies for the binary systems *o*-xylene+cyclohexane, *p*-xylene+cyclohexane and benzene+n-octane have been determined at 300.05 K at different compositions of each system using an isothermal phase change calorimeter.

Experimental

o-Xylene (Riedel), *p*-xylene (B.D.H.) and cyclohexane (B.D.H.) each of L.R. grade were distilled over sodium before use. n-Octane and benzene (each AnalaR) were used as such.

The details of the procedure adopted for the measurement of excess enthalpies using an isothermal phase change calorimeter have been described elsewhere⁸. The temperature of the water-thermostat surrounding the mixing cell was within ± 0.01 K.

Results and Discussion

The values of observed excess molar enthalpies (H^E) for the binary systems *o*-xylene+cyclohexane, *p*-xylene+cyclohexane and benzene+n-octane have been presented in Table 1 and the plots of H^E as a

function of mixture composition are given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Plots of molar excess enthalpies (H^E) at 300.05 K as a function of mole fraction (x_1): (O) *o*-xylene(1)+cyclohexane(2), (Δ) *p*-xylene(1)+cyclohexane(2) and ($\square$) benzene(1)+n-octane(2).

The H^E values are positive and symmetrical with respect to the composition for the studied systems. The magnitude of equimolar excess enthalpies are in the order: (benzene+n-octane) > (*p*-xylene+cyclohexane) > (*o*-xylene+cyclohexane). The observed positive excess enthalpies for the mixtures

TABLE 1—EXCESS MOLAR ENTHALPY (H^E) FOR SOME BINARY MIXTURES AT 300.05 K

<i>o</i> -Xylene(1) + Cyclohexane(2)		<i>p</i> -Xylene(1) + Cyclohexane		Benzene(1) + n-Octane(2)	
X_1	H^E (J mol ⁻¹)	X_1	H^E (J mol ⁻¹)	X_1	H^E (J mol ⁻¹)
0.310	431	0.308	451	0.248	588
0.426	476	0.429	538	0.387	876
0.468	487	0.499	578	0.463	930
0.581	455	0.531	570	0.565	1037
0.626	427	0.607	525	0.655	1021
0.700	385	0.700	440	0.699	975
0.808	250	0.805	349	0.789	848

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND THEORETICAL VALUES OF TS^E (J mol⁻¹) at 303.15 K

X_1	o-Xylene(1) + Cyclohexane(2)		p-Xylene(1) + Cyclohexane(2)		Benzene(1) + n-Octane(2)	
	Experi- mental	Flory's theory	Experi- mental	Flory's theory	Experi- mental	Flory's theory
0.1	—	40	71	48	155	115
0.2	68	68	126	80	301	213
0.3	108	83	172	105	468	291
0.4	137	90	209	113	582	347
0.5	150	92	246	115	661	378
0.6	131	87	215	105	703	380
0.7	104	75	133	90	687	349
0.8	67	55	72	70	575	280
0.9	30	30	9	38	286	168

*For o-xylene + cyclohexane and p-xylene + cyclohexane systems, TS^E values were calculated using H^E values at rounded mole fractions reported in this paper and the G^E values reported in Ref. 4 ; for benzene + n-octane system, G^E values taken from Ref. 9.

indicate that the mixing of components in these systems involves dispersion or van der Waals type of interaction rather than any specific donor-acceptor type of interaction.

Excess entropies calculated using the excess enthalpies reported here and the Gibbs energy data reported earlier^{4,9} are given in Table 2. Larger TS^E values for p-xylene + cyclohexane than o-xylene + cyclohexane system indicate more random mixing of molecules of unlike components in the former system than in the latter. Maximum excess entropy values among the studied systems, were observed in case of benzene + n-octane. It is attributed to the comparatively larger molecular sizes difference of the components in the mixture n-octane + benzene which leads to the large magnitude of combinatorial entropy in this system. However, in case of remaining two systems, namely, o-xylene + cyclohexane and p-xylene + cyclohexane, where the component molecules differ only slightly in their sizes, the excess entropy values are comparatively low.

Comparison with theoretical excess thermodynamic functions: The experimental excess thermodynamic data for the studied systems has been compared with the corresponding values obtained from Flory's theory².

According to this statistical treatment, a liquid mixture consisting of non-polar components of different shapes and sizes is treated on the basis of a partition function representing liquid state properties. Excess thermodynamic functions of mixtures can be calculated using the characteristic parameters which are obtainable from physical properties such as thermal expansion coefficient (α), thermal pressure coefficient (γ_1) etc. of pure components. Excess enthalpies (H^E) and entropies (S^E) may be represented by the expressions,

$$H^E = x_1 P_1^* \cdot V_1^* (1/\bar{V}_1 - 1/\bar{V}) + x_2 P_2^* \cdot V_2^* (1/\bar{V}_2 - 1/\bar{V}) + (x_1 V_1^* \cdot \theta_2/\bar{V}) X_{12} \quad (1)$$

$$TS^E = T \Delta S_{\text{comb}} - T \Delta S_{\text{id}} + TS^R \quad (2)$$

where, x_i , P_i , V_i^* and $\bar{V}_i$ represent the mole fraction, characteristic pressure, volume and reduced volume respectively of component i ($i=1, 2$). The combinatorial entropy per mole is given by

$$\Delta S_{\text{comb}} = -R(x_1 \ln \phi_1 + x_2 \ln \phi_2) \quad (3)$$

the segment fractions, ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 are defined as

$$\phi_2 = 1 - \phi_1 = \frac{X_2 V_2^*}{X_1 V_1^* + X_2 V_2^*} \quad (4)$$

and the ideal entropy of mixing is represented by the relation,

$$\Delta S_{\text{id}} = -R(x_1 \ln x_1 + x_2 \ln x_2)$$

and the residual entropy is given by

$$TS^R = -3(x_1 P_1^* V_1^* \bar{T}_1) \ln (V_1^{-1/3} - 1)/(\bar{V}^{1/3} - 1) - 3(x_2 P_2^* V_2^* \bar{T}_2) \ln (V_2^{-1/3} - 1)/(\bar{V}^{1/3} - 1) \quad (5)$$

The site fraction is given by the relation,

$$\theta_2 = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{x_1 (V_1^*)^{2/3}}{x_2 (V_2^*)^{2/3}}} \quad (6)$$

The reduced equation of state variables ($\bar{V}_i$, $\bar{T}_i$) and characteristic parameters (V_i^* , P_i^* and T_i^*) for the pure component (i) are calculated using thermal expansion coefficient (α) and thermal pressure coefficient (ν) values of each component (Table 3) as described by Flory².

The reduced parameter $\bar{V}$ and $\bar{T}$ for the mixture and the intermolecular interaction parameter X_{12} were calculated as described as follows. Using the equimolar experimental H^E value and taking $\bar{V}$ of the mixture equal to $\bar{V}^0$, the reduced volume of mixture at zero pressure,

$$\bar{V}^0 = \phi_1 \cdot \bar{V}_1 + \phi_2 \cdot \bar{V}_2 \quad (7)$$

where, ϕ_i is segment fraction of i -th component ($i=1, 2$), a first approximate value of X_{12} was calculated from equation (1). This X_{12} value was used to obtain first approximate value of $\bar{T}$ from equation (8).

TABLE 3—CHARACTERISTIC PROPERTIES OF PURE COMPONENTS USED IN FLORY'S THEORY AT 303.15 K

Component	α $\times 10^3 \text{ K}^{-1}$	β $\times 10^6$	$\bar{V}$	V^* $\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	T^* K	P^* J cm^{-3}	V^0 $\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
<i>o</i> -Xylene	0.985 ^a	82.0 ^b	1.248 0	97.59	5315	567.2	121.80
<i>p</i> -Xylene	0.989 ^a	90.8 ^b	1.248 8	99.71	5303	515.0	124.53
Cyclohexane	1.235 ^c	119.9 ^c	1.298 6	84.24	4719	528.3	109.40
<i>n</i> -Octane	1.170	—	1.285 4	127.76	4854	430.9 ^d	164.22
Benzene	1.240	—	1.298 9	69.14	4715	623.3 ^d	89.81

^aCalculated using densities at different temperatures in Ref. 10. ^bFrom Ref. 11. ^cEstimated from values given at different temperatures in Ref. 12. ^d P^* values taken from Ref. 13.

TABLE 4—VALUES OF $\bar{T}$, $\bar{V}$ AND X_{12} FOR THE MIXTURES USED IN FLORY'S THEORY AT 303.15 K

System	$\bar{T}$	$\bar{V}$	X_{12} J cm^{-3}	$V_1^* \theta_2 X_{12} / 2\bar{V}$ J mol^{-1}
<i>o</i> -Xylene+ Cyclohexane	0.060 8	1.273 8	21.15	385 (117)
<i>p</i> -Xylene+ Cyclohexane	0.061 2	1.276 1	23.76	438 (135)
Benzene+ <i>n</i> -Octane	0.064 5	1.300 4	43.72	699 (264)

in equation (1), are given in the last column of Table 4. Values in parenthesis in the same column represent the equimolar equation of state contribution (given by the first two terms in equation 1) to the total excess enthalpy. For the studied systems the contact interaction contribution to H^E dominates the equation of state contribution. Since the reduced volumes of the component molecules differ only slightly (2–4%) from each other the equation of

TABLE 5—COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND THEORETICAL VALUES OF H^E (J mol^{-1}) AT ROUNDED MOLE FRACTIONS (X_1)

X_1	<i>o</i> -Xylene(1) + Cyclohexane(2)		<i>p</i> -Xylene(1) + Cyclohexane(2)		Benzene(1) + <i>n</i> -Octane(2)	
	H_{Exptl}^E	H_{Flory}^E	H_{Exptl}^E	H_{Flory}^E	H_{Exptl}^E	H_{Flory}^E
0.1	—	191	200	—	239	298
0.2	334	333	341	375	462	548
0.3	436	432	442	491	693	747
0.4	491	488	515	547	855	888
0.5	502	502	573	573	963	963
0.6	458	476	546	545	1010	965
0.7	374	412	447	469	971	882
0.8	278	310	336	352	802	705
0.9	—	172	175	197	421	418

$$\bar{T} = (\phi_1 P_1^* \cdot \bar{T}_1 + \phi_2 P_2^* \bar{T}_2) / (\phi_1 P_1^* + \phi_2 P_2^* - \phi_1 \theta_2 X_{12}) \quad (8)$$

The $\bar{T}$ value thus obtained was used to obtain a fresh value of $\bar{V}$ from the relation,

$$(\bar{V}^{1/3} - 1) / \bar{V}^{4/3} = \bar{T} \quad (9)$$

The above iterative steps were repeated till the constant values of $\bar{V}$, $\bar{T}$ and X_{12} for a mixture were obtained (Table 4).

The characteristic properties of pure components and the values of the parameters for the mixtures are given in Tables 3 and 4 respectively. The H^E and TS^E values calculated from Flory's treatment are compared with the experimentally observed excess functions in Tables 5 and 2 respectively.

Flory's treatment predicts excess enthalpies in fair agreement with the corresponding experimental excess enthalpies for the studied systems (Table 5). Contact interaction contributions to H^E for an equimolar mixture given by the term $(x_1 v_1^* \theta_2 / \bar{V}) X_{12}$,

state contribution to H^E are positive for the studied systems. Further, the prediction of lower TS^E values than the corresponding experimental excess entropies (Table 2) is the inherent weakness of the Flory's theory.

References

1. I. PRIGOGINE, "The molecular Theory of Solutions", North Holland, Amsterdam, 1957, pp. 227-229.
2. P. J. FLORY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 1833.
3. A. J. TRESSEZANOWICZ and G. C. BENSON, *Fluid Phase Equilibria*, 1985, **23**, 117.
4. D. V. S. JAIN and O. P. YADAV, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1973, **5**, 541.
5. D. V. S. JAIN and O. P. YADAV, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 718.
6. O. P. YADAV, S. P. KHATKAR and R. C. SAINI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 306.
7. O. P. YADAV, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1989, **21**, 985.
8. D. V. S. JAIN, O. P. YADAV and S. S. GILL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 339.
9. B. SINGH, Ph. D. Thesis, Panjab University, 1970.

YADAV : EXCESS ENTHALPIES OF BINARY MIXTURES OF SOME HYDROCARBONS

10. J. TIMMERMANS, 'Physicochemical Constants of Pure Organic Compounds', Elsevier, New York, 1950 and 1965.
11. J. SINGH, H. D. PELUG and G. C. BENSON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 1939.
12. A. ABE and P. J. FLORY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 1838.
13. D. V. S. JAIN and S. SINGH, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1973, **20**, 374.